

Projects focused on Gender Equality Plans

The Funded projects

Four projects funded by the European Commission under the “Support for the Implementation of Inclusive Gender Equality Plans - HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-81” topic, have a common goal to support Gender Equality in the higher education sector.

Projects are expected to contribute to the following expected outcomes:

- Enhance the **reputation, attractiveness, inclusiveness, and research excellence** of less advanced institutions as a result of implementing inclusive gender equality plans.
- **Transform institutions** to advance inclusive gender equality within the European Research Area (ERA).
- The **institutional change strategy** implemented through gender equality plans has had very positive impacts on many research organisations and has been a catalyser at the national and EU level, as the latest ERA progress report has shown. However, there is a heterogeneity in the implementation of Gender Equality Plans across the EU, and persisting structural barriers in R&I institutions which must be addressed, through a renewed approach.
- The **inclusion scheme** aims to strengthen and go beyond the minimum requirements for a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) as defined in Horizon Europe eligibility criteria, and to support the implementation of inclusive GEPs in line with the new ERA Communication and gender equality objectives.

Four granted projects collaborated to discuss how they can support their shared objective of promoting and attaining gender equality. They aim to achieve this through innovative and inclusive Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) that create a safe environment in universities. Joint efforts to raise awareness and share experiences will aid in the accomplishment of gender equality goals.

Brainstorming for the joint efforts began at the start of the summer of 2023 and continued in October. As one of their first joint activity, the sister projects united together to create social media campaigns and increase awareness, inform, and increase the overall impact of their projects.

On the occasion of the **International Day for the Elimination of Violence against Women 2023**, a joint awareness-raising campaign on gender-based violence in ERA was started by the 4 sister projects, AGRIPGEP, BUDGET-IT, NEXUS, and SUPPORTER, that ran from November 24th to December 16th. DG RTD featured and shared the posts on their channels. Following the success of this social media campaign, similar joint campaigns are planned alongside projects, information, and joint training.

SISTER PROJECTS of the TOPIC

SUPPORTER "SecUring sPORTs Education thRough innovative and inclusive Gender Equality Plans" advances inclusive gender+ equality within the European Research Area (ERA). It supports 8 higher education institutions from Central and Eastern Europe to develop tailored intersectional, innovative, inclusive, and impactful gender equality plans (4I-GEPs). It also explicitly addresses gender-based violence including sexual harassment (GBV). Building on state-of-the-art knowledge and the expertise of advanced gender+ equality institutions, SUPPORTER co-creates an innovative capacity-building and mutual learning programme, delivering support and mentoring towards the development of the 4I-GEPs. Project website: <https://www.supporter-project.eu/>

BUDGET-IT "Building Gender Equality Through Gender Budgeting for Institutional Transformation" is a three-year project designed to use gender+ budgeting to transform institutions to advance inclusive gender+ equality and enhance the reputation, inclusiveness, and research excellence of 9 organisations (5 research producing organisations and 4 local municipalities) of the widening countries of Bosnia, Serbia and Turkey assisted by leading university counterparts in Italy and Spain. Project website: <https://budget-it.eu/>

NEXUS "Twinning Research and Innovation Institutions to Design and Implement Inclusive GEPs" project co-designs, implements, monitors, and evaluates innovative and targeted actions aimed at bridging inclusivity gaps in nine research organisations and their respective R&I ecosystems to bolster institutional change through the development of inclusive Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in intersectional and intersectoral directions.

AGRIGEP "Assessment and implementation of Agriculture and Life Science Universities' first Gender Equality Plans in widening countries" project, through the joint efforts of six partners, including universities from 3 widening countries performs a responsible assessment of the current status of their GEP implementation, improving capabilities through intensive capacity building with the help of 3 mentor organisations. They develop and implement an agriculture and life-science targeted GEP with sectorial-specific measures and strategies. Project website: <https://agrigeu.eu/>

